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Recent advancements in the tau reconstruction and identification techniques in CMS

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Abstract

Tau leptons play a crucial role in studies of the Higgs boson and searches for Beyond the Standard Model physics at the present LHC and in its high luminosity upgrade. This talk presents the latest advancements in the reconstruction and identification of hadronic decays of tau leptons at the CMS experiment, both at the online and offline levels. The tau identification algorithm deployed for the early Run 3 data-taking period, based on a deep convolutional neural network with domain adaptation, showcases significantly improved discrimination of genuine hadronic tau decays against mis-identified quark and gluon jets, electrons, and muons. During live data-taking, a simplified version of the algorithm is used to select events with tau leptons at the High Level Trigger (HLT). The performance and calibration of both algorithms using early Run 3 data are presented. Many CMS physics analyses involving tau leptons are expected to benefit from these improvements. Alternative approaches to identify hadronic taus combined with jet flavour, based on graph neural networks and particle transformers, are also covered. Additionally, the dedicated techniques used to reconstruct and identify displaced tau leptons originating from long-lived particle decays using graph neural networks are discussed.

1 Introduction

The CMS Collaboration [1,2] at the CERN LHC has a long history of physics analyses requiring the precise and accurate reconstruction of tau leptons. These include measurements of the Higgs boson production [3,4] and properties under CP symmetry [5], which relies on the identification of the tau decay products and their angular distributions [6], the measurement of the tau polarization [7] and anomalous magnetic moment [8,9], and searches for new physics in final states with tau leptons [10–12]. This rich program is supported by continuous advancements in reconstruction and identification techniques deployed by the CMS Collaboration, the most recent of which are presented in these proceedings.

2 Tau Reconstruction and Identification in CMS

Tau leptons produced in “standard” topologies, i.e., prompt production via Drell–Yan, Yukawa, or charge current electroweak interactions, generally decay before reaching the innermost layers of the CMS detector [1,2]. They are therefore reconstructed from their decay products. Leptonically decaying tau leptons are reconstructed following the standard reconstruction techniques for prompt electrons and muons [13–16]; their identification is inferred based on the global

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event topology (properties of the dilepton system, presence of energy imbalance in the transverse plane, etc.). Isolated hadronically decaying tau leptons (τ_h) candidates are reconstructed by the hadron-plus-strip (HPS) algorithm [17], which selects a combination of 1 or 3 tracks with energy deposits in the calorimeters, to identify the tau decay channel. Neutral pions are reconstructed as strips with dynamic size in η - ϕ from the reconstructed electrons and photons. The HPS algorithm was tuned to prioritize the efficiency of the reconstruction and is used in conjunction with dedicated algorithms to identify genuine τ_h decays from jets originating from the hadronization of quarks or gluons, and from electrons or muons. The convolutional neural network (CNN) DEEPTAU has been used [18] for this purpose since the end of the LHC Run 2. Information from all individual reconstructed particles near the τ_h axis is combined with properties of the τ_h candidate and the event.

2.1 Recent Advancements in Tau Identification

The DEEPTAU algorithm has received major updates at the start of Run 3. This new version [19], labeled v2.5, was optimized in terms of dataset preparation and hyperparameter optimization with respect to its predecessor (v2.1). The major update is a domain adaptation subnetwork, tasked with ensuring that the DEEPTAU performance is unaffected by potential mismodelling in the Monte Carlo simulation used for its training. This results in an improved simulation-to-data agreement for the DEEPTAU classifiers, as exemplified in Figs. 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Distribution of the DEEPTAU discriminator against quark and gluon jets before (left) and after (right) domain adaptation, for the dataset used to train the domain adaptation [19].

Figure 2: Visible mass distribution for a muon and τ_h system for 2024 (left) and 2025 (right) data [20]. For 2024, data correspond to an integrated luminosity of 109 fb^{-1} . For 2025, data correspond to an integrated luminosity of 26.5 fb^{-1} , collected up to the 23rd of July 2025.

Fig. 1 compares the against-jet classifier of DEEPTAU with the domain adaptation being included or excluded, while Fig. 2 shows the resulting simulation-to-data agreement during 2024 and in the first half of 2025 [20], presenting the invariant mass of a muon and τ_h system in the absence of dedicated calibrations on the τ_h candidate, underlying the accuracy of the modelling of the DEEPTAUv2.5 algorithm.

3 Alternative Strategies for Tau Identification

An alternative strategy for the identification of genuine τ_h candidates developed in CMS: the simultaneous classification of jet origin, treating the τ_h candidates as jets. This “unified jet tagging” philosophy provides a few advantages, such as an inherent modelling of the correlation between the identification of different objects, an easier optimization for the selection efficiency to prioritize the rejection of specific sources of contamination, and a general concentration of computing resources. Two algorithms have been introduced: PNET [21], a graph neural network representing jets as a “particle cloud”, and UPART [22], which relies on a transformer architecture. As the jet classification performed by these algorithms is not limited to τ_h candidates selected by HPS, a dedicated comparison [23] that accounts for different reconstruction and pileup suppression techniques [24–26], was needed to estimate their efficiency and background rejection accurately. Fig. 3 shows the rejection of jets and electrons of the presented algorithms as a function of the identification for genuine τ_h candidates. The algorithms perform differently across misidentified objects, highlighting how exploring different machine learning architectures can help improve the identification of τ_h candidates.

Figure 3: ROC curves illustrating the performance of the DEEPTAU, PNET, and UPART algorithms to discriminate quark and gluon jets (left) and electrons (right) misidentified as τ_h candidates [23]. The efficiencies are evaluated taking into account the preceding reconstruction and pileup mitigation algorithms used, labeled HPS, CHS, and PUPPI [17, 24–26].

4 Taus in Nonstandard Topologies

Additional algorithms have been deployed in CMS to target topologies not adequately covered by the standard reconstruction and identification techniques:

- DISTAU [27], a PNET-like algorithm targeting τ_h candidates produced displaced from the primary interaction vertex;
- BOOSTED DEEPTAU [28], a CNN algorithm using the same architecture as DEEPTAU dedicated to τ_h candidates produced as part of a boosted $\tau\tau$ system where the decay products of the two tau leptons overlap;

- a modified version of HPS dedicated to low- p_T τ_h candidates recorded in the scouting data stream [29], accompanied by a dedicated energy flow neural network named TAUNET [30].

Representative distributions to showcase these dedicated algorithms are presented in Fig. 4

Figure 4: Left and middle: Jet rejection vs τ_h identification efficiency for the DISTAU graph network at high displacement [27], and for the BOOSTED DEEPTAU CNN algorithm at high p_T [28], respectively. Right: calibration of the low- p_T τ_h reconstruction algorithm using the $\Upsilon \rightarrow \tau_\mu \tau_h$ resonance [30].

5 Tau Identification at the HLT

With the exception of the scouting data flow, which relies only on information available at the hardware level trigger [31] of the CMS apparatus, proton-proton collisions are recorded based on a software-based high level trigger (HLT) system [32, 33]. Run 3 saw the deployment of improved neural-network-based algorithms to identify τ_h candidates at different stages of the HLT reconstruction [34]: L2TAUNNTAG and an online version of DEEPTAU. Their relative improvement with respect to the cut-based algorithms used in Run 2 is shown in Fig. 5 for the trigger algorithm that requires the simultaneous identification of two τ_h candidates.

Figure 5: Efficiency as a function of the τ_h candidate p_T evaluated on the di- τ_h trigger algorithm at the L1+L2 stage (left) and with the full L1+HLT system (right) [34].

6 Summary

These proceedings provide an overview of recent advancements in reconstruction and identification techniques for hadronically decaying tau leptons deployed by the CMS Collaboration. These advancements both increase the overall efficiency in identifying tau leptons and widen the scope of physics analyses to previously unaddressed topologies.

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